

EFFECTIVENESS OF STUDENTS' ENTREPRENEURIAL SKILLS DEVELOPMENT THROUGH CLIL TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract. The article describes the ideas of ensuring the active participation of students in the educational process on the basis of entrepreneurship-oriented teaching methods based on the effectiveness of developing entrepreneurial skills of students with the help of CLIL technologies. Also, many educational possibilities of education related to teaching foreign languages for entrepreneurship, attracting students to training, motivation, and raising self-confidence in students are discussed. has been done, while at the same time it reveals the factors that affect the creation of jobs to a certain extent.

Key words: CLIL technologies, entrepreneurship, method, independent thinking, creativity, independent reading, cooperation, communication.

Introduction. Today, in a number of developed countries, great experiences have been used in the application of business-oriented CLIL technologies that increase the educational and creative activities of students and guarantee the effectiveness of the educational process in English language classes, and the basis of this experience forming methods are called interactive methods based on an integrative approach.

Literature analysis and methodology

In the world, a number of scientific researches are being carried out to prepare students for life activities by improving the pedagogical mechanisms of teaching foreign languages for entrepreneurship with the help of CLIL technologies. In international practice, teaching foreign languages with the help of CLIL technologies for entrepreneurship plays an important role in creating new jobs and reducing unemployment, increasing the volume of service provision, and solving social and economic problems. Development of innovative methods and tools based on entrepreneurship to prepare students for entrepreneurial activities and socio-economic changes in the conditions of qualitative renewal of educational programs, methodical bases and mechanisms of teaching foreign languages for entrepreneurship on the basis of CLIL technologies based on value creation design is of particular importance.

Results and Discussion

In the conditions of the market economy, improving the methodological basis of teaching foreign languages with the help of CLIL technologies for entrepreneurship in the future is competitive in the labor market, responsible,

well-versed in their profession and related fields of activity, able to work effectively at the level of world standards, relevant knowledge determines the satisfaction of the needs of the person in possession.

In order to meet the needs of the economy of Uzbekistan for entrepreneurial personnel, it is necessary to develop a more effective program of teaching foreign languages for entrepreneurship with the help of CLIL technologies. This program should take into account the promising trends in the formation of practical entrepreneurial skills in students and the growth of the number of self-employed young people, as well as the expansion of the use of various forms of training of highly specialized entrepreneurs.

The purpose of using CLIL technologies in teaching English is to teach future pedagogues to choose effective methods and tools based on existing pedagogical laws and specific conditions, mainly the educational process, based on entrepreneurship. Due to the development of the student's personality, his independent cognitive activity during the educational process, there is a need to improve educational methods. In the teaching of English, methods such as "Working with groups", "Discussion", "Problem teaching", "Brainstorming", as well as working with tables, writing works expressing independent opinion, writing essays using CLIL technologies. increases entrepreneurial activity. Through these methods, it is possible to grow and develop a person's creative, technical, and entrepreneurial abilities, and to activate their educational activities. To do this, participants are encouraged to be creative, even if they accept proposals that are far from reality; all ideas and suggestions, no matter how unusual they may seem, are written down; time is determined, they share the proposals they have developed with each other. The use of these methods has given good results in developed countries.

First of all, the teacher pays attention to the content and quality of the lessons in order to increase the interest of the students. For this, he tries to make children think and activate them. The student is led to discussion in order to become an active participant in the classroom learning process rather than a receiver of ready-made knowledge. Distinctive aspects of the content: the educational material is introduced in a large volume, the materials are arranged in blocks, the educational material is drawn in the form of a basic scheme and overview.

Conclusion/Recommendations

The development of entrepreneurial skills of students in English language classes with the help of CLIL technologies will meet the needs of a person who will be competitive in the future labor market, responsible, well-versed in his

profession and related fields of activity, able to work efficiently at the level of world standards, and acquire relevant knowledge. defines. Improving the methodical basis of teaching foreign languages with the help of CLIL technologies for entrepreneurship will ensure a new qualitative level of demonstration, practical explanation and the use of reproductive methods in education, the form of education, the scope of knowledge of students serves to expand, develops independent work skills.

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